

THE FUTURE OF E-COMMERCE MARKETING IN THE AGE OF SUSTAINABLE AND ETHICAL CONSUMERISM

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ABSTRACT

This research aims at examining the impact of sustainable and ethical e-commerce marketing approach with an emphasis on getting insights on the impact of transparency, sustainability and the supply chain-evaluate on the consumers' purchasing behaviour. Based on the Diffusion of Innovation Theory and SVAB Model, the present study investigated consumers' perception and intentions to engage in ethical marketing practices.

A quantitative research design was adopted in this study, an online structured questionnaire, with 253 participants being conveniently sampled. The analytical tools of the study included the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences software that facilitated a search for trends, correlations and consumer preferences. Originally, convenience sampling helped to collect data with fewer hurdles, but it inherent biased connected with respondents' availability and readiness to complete the survey that bound the study's conclusions by these flaws.

These findings indicate consumers have a high sensitivity to ethical issues such as waste disposal and child labour and thus seek to purchase products from milk brands that uphold environmental and ethical business practices in packaging and supply-chain respectively. It also improves the trustworthiness of the brand, the loyalty of the consumers, and the competitive advantage in the marketplace.

Nevertheless, given the foregoing limitations, such as the use of self-administered questionnaires, the study carries important implications for businesses, policymakers and researchers. Therefore, it underlines the necessity of cooperation to enhance sustainable e-commerce practices and suggests the implementation of further research based on various methodologies alongside more geographical samples for further confirmation of the research results.

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Since e-commerce platforms have grown at a rapid pace in recent years, the business environment has changed tremendously. With unmatched ease, accessibility, and variety for customers globally, these digital marketplaces

have completely transformed the way products and services are purchased and sold. Parallel to this exponential development, e-commerce has raised some doubts concerning ethical and environmental impacts. Speaking about sustainability or ethical consumption, technology

combined with commerce offers new opportunities but also puts new obstacles in the way-mitigating or being incapable of taking advantage of WANG et al., 2021. The e-commerce website, while offering opportunities for consumers to make enlightened choices, selling more ecologically friendly products, and providing less carbon-emission logistic options, on the other side might. On the other hand, the proliferation of online shopping has raised concerns about the environmental impact of packaging waste, energy consumption in data centers, and exploitation of labour in global value chains (Haryanti and Subriadi, 2022). In this respect, there is an increasing need to consider the development of e-marketing within the context of ethical and sustainable consumption. Businesses have to adapt their marketing strategies according to these principles, as customers become increasingly aware of the social and environmental impacts of the products they purchase. E-commerce companies must understand customer attitudes, preferences, and behaviors about sustainability to be competitive and socially responsible in the digital era (Štofejová et al., 2023). Moreover, global regulatory bodies have begun to implement stricter regulations on e-tailers with the aim of ensuring that data privacy laws, labour standards, and environmental laws are complied with. The dynamic nature of regulations exacerbates the challenges faced by e-marketers in balancing myriad moral and legal responsibilities with the objective of profitability and competitiveness (Rao et al., 2021).

Problem Statement

E-commerce is the root of so many pressing ethical and ecological issues that really urgently need attention. Online shopping offers unprecedented accessibility and convenience, but at the cost of environmental degradation due to energy use and wasteful packaging, and unsustainable supply chain practices just get worse. Further, there are the ethical considerations regarding fair labour laws and employee rights regarding labour exploitation in international e-commerce supply chains (Štofejová et al., 2023). The environmental and ethical aspects of e-commerce marketing need to be addressed immediately, as consumer knowledge of these concerns grows. To fulfil

customer needs and stay competitive in the digital marketplace, e-commerce enterprises may successfully include sustainable and ethical practices into their marketing strategy (Kemppainen et al., 2021). However, there is a lack of thorough research on this topic. By examining the future of e-commerce marketing in the era of ethical and sustainable consumption, this research seeks to close this gap.

Research Question(s)

In order to fulfil the research identified gap, the below question has been intended to answer in this study:

How do e-commerce marketing strategies that incorporate sustainability and ethical considerations influence consumer purchase intentions in the digital marketplace?

Purpose of the Study

This research aims to explore how ethical and sustainable factors might be included into e-commerce marketing tactics to impact customer buying decisions. The findings will help organisations develop strategies that effectively address changing consumer needs. The following are the research objectives of this study in order to accomplish the purpose of the research:

- To analyse how customers, feel about ethical and sustainable e-commerce practices.
- To determine the main elements influencing ethical and sustainable consumer behaviour.
- To analyse how well e-commerce marketing techniques are working to advance ethical and sustainable consumption.
- To examine how e-commerce operations are affected by supply chain sustainability and legal compliance.
- To provide advice and insights to help companies create ethical and sustainable marketing strategies for the online market, which will eventually increase customer satisfaction and brand loyalty.

Significance of Study

Contributions to both academics and business highlight the importance of this research. Academically, it closes a gap in the body of knowledge by advancing our understanding of

how e-commerce marketing and sustainable/ethical consumption interact (Štofejová et al., 2023). Practically speaking, it provides information that helps companies create more socially conscious marketing plans, improving their reputation and ability to compete in the digital market. Furthermore, policymakers might use the data to guide regulations that support ethical and sustainable e-commerce activities. In the end, our research aims to promote sustainable corporate practices and encourage consumer behaviour that is socially and ecologically conscientious in order to positively influence society (Rao et al., 2021).

Literature Review

Diffusion of Innovation Theory

Diffusion of Innovation Theory, by Lee (2021), describes the way new ideas, products, or behaviors get adopted within a social system: innovators, early adopters, early majority, late majority, and laggards. The major drivers to adopt any innovation are perceived benefits derived, compatibility, complexity, trialability, and observability. Ethical and sustainable e-commerce uses this theory to introduce, receive, and spread innovative sustainability initiatives among customers. Shahid, 2022; Nordhoff et al., 2021. Goh & Sigala (2020) state that when the product is aligned with consumers' beliefs and lifestyles, there is a better adoption of sustainable choices in online purchasing behavior.

The SVAB Model

The SVAB model of Sustainability-Value-Attitude-Behaviour embeds the ideas of ecological psychology and marketing and advertising in trying to understand better the associations between sustainability ideals, attitudes, and behaviours (Erul et al., 2023). Conceptually, the idea suggests a person's attitude toward nature-friendly procedures or products is built in upon attitudinal values associated inherently with sustainability, and such formed attitude influences their purchasing decisions (Wijaya et al., 2021; Jacobs et al., 2018). In the realm of ethical and sustainable e-commerce marketing strategies, the SVAB Model offers a complete structure to understand the mental processes behind sustainable consumer behavior (Kim et al. 2024). Also, the SVAB Model suggests that, in e-commerce, consumer

purchasing patterns are affected by views on sustainability (Sadiq et al. 2022).

Empirical Reviews

According to Kemppainen et al. (2021), there is a need to understand the customers' behavior about the issues of sustainability and ethics in this fast-growing e-commerce world. In regard to the sustainability of cross-border e-commerce, context signals for online purchasing affect customers' intentions to buy, as stated by the study of Xiao et al. (2019). In the present study, four signals, online promotion, content marketing, tailored suggestion, and social review, are considered the strong persuaders of purchase intentions. Data from 372 cross-border online customers in China are analysed, and the findings point out how the online shopping environment acts as a key determinant for influencing customer attitudes and behaviors in the context of international e-commerce environments.

The research of Anantasiska et al. (2022) focuses on how the social media marketing activities are influencing young e-commerce customers' purchase intention. Based on the authors, therefore, social media marketing activities have a positive influence on brand image, brand awareness, and brand preference; these are factors which affect purchase intention. This present study represents data from 270 Shopee customers aged between 13 and 15 years from Indonesia. This will highlight how, as a tool of marketing, social media in e-commerce plays a major role in influencing customer behavior.

The mediating role of CRM has been analyzed by Yunus et al. in research undertaken in 2022 as the link between digital marketing and online trust for the generation of the intent of an online purchase of e-commerce customers of Banda Aceh, Indonesia. By obtaining the sample size of a 150 respondent's research has indicated the mediating effect of CRM upon online-generated trust and digital marketing against their respective online buy intention thus, giving due significance to the role efficient CRM strategies have in boosting online purchase intentions.

Research Framework

This paper, in the context of the sustainability of e-commerce, has its research approach designed to clearly explain the intricate interaction that

happens among a set of independent factors and customers' purchase intentions. (Haryanti & Subriadi, 2022). The current study, therefore, supported by the Sustainability-Value-Attitude-Behaviour Model and the diffusion of innovation theory, which identify variables affecting the rate of adoption and diffusion of any innovation, tries to provide comprehensive insight into sustainable consumer behavior in the digital

marketplace. Min et al. (2021); Jacobs et al. (2018). This study, therefore, seeks to contribute to the understanding of sustainable customer behaviour and provide recommendations on how to create an effective marketing strategy that supports ethics and sustainability in e-commerce through the in-depth examination of the outlined factors and their relationships. Figure 1, below, is the framework of the study:

Figure 1 Research Framework

Hypotheses Development

Consumer Online Purchase Intentions

Consumer purchase intentions are helpful to develop behavior, in particular in sustainable e-commerce. Influenced by personal traits, ethics, and concern for the environment, such intentions reflect a will towards socially and ecologically conscious purchasing, as pointed out by Chetioui et al. (2020) and Khan et al. (2023). The consumer prefers those firms that stand for ethical standards and sustainability. Even these intentions are affected by external factors such as social interactions and marketing. Strategies for digital marketing emphasize promoting sustainability, which can bring great returns from consumers aware of their responsibilities (Waheed et al., 2018). Accordingly, businesses using an understanding of consumer beliefs within an organization would improve trust and loyalty of their consumers. In this regard, positive purchasing intention will enforce ethical practices and the cultivation of responsible consumption by e-commerce.

Green Consumer Attitudes

Green consumer attitudes refer to the values, beliefs, and preferences of individuals towards environment-friendly products and practices. The former show commitment to the environment in the choices they make

concerning purchases and may lead to more awareness regarding sustainability issues (Mohd Suki, 2016). Such consumers have very strong green attitudes: they will tend to seek measurable variables like recyclability and energy efficiency in a product (Ali et al., 2023), and therefore would demand more sustainable products. Understanding and responding to e-commerce green attitudes is very relevant to influence sustainable purchasing behavior (Shimul et al., 2022). Online businesses may employ these methods include offering green alternatives and information on sustainability practices and tailor-made messages that suit different categories of environmentally-conscious consumers (Costa et al., 2021). According to the discussions, the first hypothesis of the study is:

H1: Green consumer attitude significantly impact the consumer purchase intention in the digital marketplace.

Ethical Brand Perception

According to Wang et al. (2021), ethical brand perception encompasses consumers' perspectives concerning the ethical conduct of a company, its social responsibility, and its commitments to ethical values; hence, it affects consumer behavior with particular regard to purchase decisions. Hence, today, consumers seek brands that conform to their value systems and exhibit

clear devotion to sustainable development or social responsibility (Vuong & Khanh Giao, 2020). E-commerce brands develop positive ethical brand perceptions through integrating sustainability into brand identity, adopting clear-cut business practices, as well as engaging in CSR initiatives. The result is credibility, trust, and consumer loyalty for differentiated brands in a competitive market and that attract socially conscious customers who are actually considering the ethics in their purchasing style (Li et al., 2021). Thus, the second hypothesis of the study reads:

H2: Ethical brand perception significantly impact the consumer purchase intention in the digital marketplace.

Digital Marketing Green Campaigns

Research also pointed toward Digital Marketing Green Campaigns as one way to influence attitudes and purchase behavior towards the virtual economy (Ali et al., 2023). These campaigns, focusing on sustainability and environmental accountability, positively impacted consumers (Majeed et al. 2022). Green marketing communications, like eco-labelling, green branding, and greenish packaging, demonstrate functional but vital significance impacts on consumers' willingness to buy green products. Eco-labels as well as reviews further reinforce this effect significantly among younger generations including generation Z (Panopoulos et al., 2022).

Consumers have been shown by research to be much more willing than others to purchase products as a result of the brand concerning environmental sustainability (Costa et al., 2021). More and more aware of the impact of their purchases on the environment have people because of the shift (Ali et al., 2023). In consequence, the organizations that quickly and efficiently integrate green marketing communications into their online marketing communication can enhance the brand image of their organizations and develop consumers' loyalty towards it, which ultimately enhances their purchase intention (Majeed et al., 2022).

H3: Digital Marketing Green Campaigns significantly impact the consumer purchase intention in the digital marketplace.

E-commerce Trustworthiness

According to Zhao et al. (2020), e-commerce trustworthiness is considered to be the perceptions of customers concerning the reliability, security, and legitimacy of online shopping places or platforms. Things such as transaction security, credibility of the site, and reputation of the vendor help to foster consumer confidence in conducting business with digital media (Tikhomirova et al., 2021). Secure payment methods, professional website design, and positive endorsements are most important in increasing e-commerce trustworthiness (Gunawan & Septianie, 2021). According to this discussion, the fourth hypothesis of the study is: H4: E-commerce trustworthiness significantly impact the consumer purchase intention in the digital marketplace.

Social Influence

Influence in society is a category through which attitudes and behaviors are modified among individuals by others in their social networks. It includes normative influence that makes individual peoples conform to social norms in an attempt at acceptance or the evasion of rejection. Informational influence also has its important impact whereby people go ahead seeking advice and it influences decision-making, and the forming of opinions (Bylok, 2022). Social influence in e-commerce simply denotes peer endorsement, online reviews, and influencer marketing that manipulates purchasing decisions of consumers (Zaremozhzabieh et al., 2021). Social media enhance the same process by making interaction and recommendations happen within the context of virtual social networks and thus cause a shaping behavior of consumers in the digital market (Khwaja et al., 2021). Going by this discussion, the fifth hypothesis of the study is as follows:

H5: Social influence significantly impact the consumer purchase intention in the digital marketplace.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Approach

The focus of this research is on identifying levels and evaluating the impact of sustainable and ethical concerns on consumer buying behaviour in e-commerce context, the researcher chooses a quantitative research methodology. The

quantitative approach is selected due to the possibility of making statistical comparisons and to be able to generalize the results to a larger population group. This approach allows the collection of quantitative data which can be quantified and analysed to derive a relationship or interaction between two variables or among several variables (Ryser, 2021). The study is also exploratory in nature; its objective here is to systematically depict and understand the profile and behaviour of e-commerce consumers with regard to sustainability and ethical issues.

Therefore, the research intends to bring a comprehensive view of consumer current state of mind and behaviour to enhance understanding from an empirical perspective. Moreover, the study employs the deductive research approach, whereby the hypothesis already formulated is used as a starting point and data is gathered to either support or reject these hypotheses (Casula, Rangarajan & Shields, 2021). This method is appropriate for this research since it seeks to expand on previous theories including the Diffusion of Innovation Theory as well as the SVAB Model, to the sphere of e-commerce with the aim of determining their applicability in the current exploration.

Research Design

The first and the main approach in the development of the research is the survey method of data gathering; this method was chosen as it allows for the rapid collection of a significant amount of data from a large number of respondents. This primary data collection technique refers to the use of structured questionnaires, which are administered to consumers of e-commerce firms with an aim of establishing their attitudes and behaviours concerning sustainable and ethical consumption (Taherdoost, 2021). Survey method of data collection is used in the study this is because it enables organizing the data in a more standardized manner as compared to other methods of data collection. Another source of data is secondary data that can be used for literature review to have a detailed insight into the prior research done on the topic under investigation as well as different theories covering the area of the study.

The literature review assists in the construction of the survey instrument and provides

contextualization for the results within the scholarly and applied literature. Thus, the use of the primary and secondary data collection methods contributes to making the research design more robust as it incorporates both the new empirical findings and the theories. The use of both quantitative and qualitative data collection methods increases the rigour and credibility of the study as it offers comprehensive understanding of the research problem.

Sampling Design

This methodology involves the inability to use a probability criterion to select participants as the study adopts the convenience sampling technique. This technique is selected because of its usability and feasibility especially when focusing on a particular category of e-commerce consumers who are easily reachable and willing to be interviewed. Convenience sampling is advantageous since it is faster and does not require much time to complete; it is useful for this research as it seeks to elicit opinions from a large pool of online consumers (Obilor, 2023). Although this method of sampling can result in a biased sample due to the fact that the participants are not randomly selected, this method is suitable for exploratory research where the objective is to find out the existence of trends or patterns and not the extent of these trends or patterns in the entire population. The sample size is calculated considering the requirements of statistical significance necessary for further analysis, let it be enough for examining the research hypotheses and for obtaining reliable results.

Instrument of Data Collection

A structured questionnaire will act as the primary method of data collection aimed at identifying the different aspects of sustainable and ethical consumption in e-commerce. The structured questionnaire also consists of categorical questions aimed at collecting basic demographic characteristics of the respondents and a set of Likert scale items to measure the relevant attitudes, perceptions, and behaviours. Likert scale is a 5-point scale that has labels of “strongly disagree” to “strongly agree,” which can be used to represent the degree of the agreement or disagreement to the statements relating to the research variables. These items are developed based on the literature review so that they capture

the appropriate construct being measured such as green consumer attitudes, ethical brand perception, digital marketing green campaigns, e-commerce trustworthiness, social influence. This is because the structured format provided in the questionnaire enables provision of standardized responses across all the questionnaires, implying reliability and validity of the collected data. The instrument will then be subjected to the pilot testing phase before finalizing the questions and finalizing on them to ensure that the data required for the study as per the research questions has been captured well.

Procedure of Data Collection

The research data is collected with the help of an online questionnaire, which is posted on social media with a link to the Google Forms survey. This method has been chosen for its effectiveness in reaching a large and various audience of e-commerce consumers not very expensively. The online survey format is basically easy and available to the respondents by which they can complete the survey at any convenient time and at any convenient place by which they get motivated to respond to survey questions, which increases the response rates. The survey link is shared on social media sites because these sites have a large membership base, and because members are likely to be active shoppers online. The distribution strategy involves sharing the link to the survey in groups, forums, and pages where one is most likely to find e-commerce consumers. This approach enhances the possibility of reaching the intended audience thus ensuring maximum responses to the survey hence increasing the chances of getting a representative sample of the target population. The duration for data collection is established to enable the accumulation of an adequate number of responses for proper scrutiny of the variables in the research.

Statistical Technique

The data is then analysed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences otherwise known as SPSS, a software program that is used to perform various tests and to analyze data. The initial testing involves reliability analysis to determine internal consistency of the

questionnaires which is commonly done using Cronbach alpha (Kennedy, 2022). Descriptive statistics can now be calculated, these will then give the frequency distribution of the Respondents age and gender and an estimate of the overall attitude and behaviour of the sample towards the online shopping. Pie charts and other figures are employed as tools to present important conclusions and guide the presentation in order to enhance the audience's understanding of the data. Pearson's correlation analysis is used to test the hypothesis and determine the correlations between the consumer attitudes, perception of ethical brands, digital marketing strategies, e-commerce credibility and social influence and the consumer purchase intentions. The hypotheses are tested, and the degree and direction of the impact of each of the independent variables on consumers' buying behaviour is assessed by performing Regression analysis. Employing extensive statistical data, this paper aims to unravel the key considerations that support consumers' responsible and ethical consumption of commodities through online platforms through addressing business and policy making strategies.

Results and Findings

Following chapter presents the results and findings of the study, focusing on the analysis of the impact of various factors—such as green consumer attitude, ethical brand perception, digital marketing green campaigns, trustworthiness, and social influence—on consumer purchase intention in the digital marketplace. The chapter outlines the statistical tests conducted, provides insights from the regression analysis, and discusses the acceptance or rejection of the proposed hypotheses based on the findings.

Demographic Statistic

This section presents the demographic profile of respondents based on four key variables: gender, age, education level, and occupation. Each category is analysed through frequency distributions and cumulative percentages to provide a comprehensive understanding of the survey participants' characteristics.

Table 1 Gender

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	131	51.8	51.8	51.8
	Female	122	48.2	48.2	100.0
	Total	253	100.0	100.0	

The gender distribution shows a nearly equal representation of males and females, with males constituting 51.8% and females 48.2% of the sample. This balance indicates minimal gender

disparity, making the findings potentially applicable to both genders. The cumulative percentage confirms the total sample of 253 respondents.

Table 2 Age

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Less than 21	45	17.8	17.8	17.8
	21 to 30	56	22.1	22.1	39.9
	31 to 40	38	15.0	15.0	54.9
	41 to 50	60	23.7	23.7	78.7
	Above 50	54	21.3	21.3	100.0
	Total	253	100.0	100.0	

Respondents are fairly distributed across age groups, with the largest group (23.7%) aged 41–50. Those above 50 (21.3%) and 21–30 (22.1%) also represent significant portions. The smallest

segment is under 21 (17.8%). This diverse age range reflects a balanced demographic, with insights applicable to various life stages.

Table 3 Education

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Matriculation/O level	42	16.6	16.6	16.6
	Intermediate/A level	49	19.4	19.4	36.0
	Undergraduate	56	22.1	22.1	58.1
	Graduate	55	21.7	21.7	79.8
	Doctorate	51	20.2	20.2	100.0
	Total	253	100.0	100.0	

Respondents have a broad educational background, with undergraduates (22.1%) slightly more represented, followed closely by graduates (21.7%) and doctorates (20.2%). A

smaller percentage hold matriculation/O-level (16.6%) or intermediate/A-level (19.4%) qualifications, indicating a moderately high educational profile within the sample.

Table 4 Occupation

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Employee	82	32.4	32.4	32.4
	Own Business	81	32.0	32.0	64.4
	Student	90	35.6	35.6	100.0
	Total	253	100.0	100.0	

Occupations are evenly distributed, with students (35.6%) forming the largest group, followed by employees (32.4%) and business owners (32.0%).

This equal distribution ensures varied perspectives in the analysis, particularly from younger and working populations.

Descriptive Profile of the Data

Table 5 Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Green Consumer Attitude	253	1.20	4.60	3.1233	.66282
Ethical Brand Perception	253	1.00	4.75	3.0208	.69922
Digital Marketing Green Campaigns	253	1.00	5.00	2.8827	.96035
Trustworthiness	253	1.00	4.50	2.8864	.72831
Social Influence	253	1.50	4.33	3.0178	.57889
Consumer Online Purchase Intention	253	1.60	4.80	3.0775	.66596
Valid N (listwise)	253				

The above Table 4.5 represents the descriptive statistics of the data collected through the questionnaire survey. According to the table, all variables (Green Consumer Attitude, Ethical Brand Perception, Digital Marketing Green Campaigns, Trustworthiness, Social Influence, and Consumer Online Purchase Intention) have comparable mean values, indicating responses tend to cluster around these averages. The mean scores range from 2.8827 (Digital Marketing Green Campaigns) to 3.1233 (Green Consumer

Attitude), reflecting moderate agreement among participants.

The standard deviations are also within a reasonable range, from 0.57889 (Social Influence) to 0.96035 (Digital Marketing Green Campaigns), demonstrating relatively low variability in responses. This consistency in standard deviation suggests that the data is reliable, with responses closely centred around their respective means, reflecting homogeneity in participants' perceptions and behaviours.

Validation of Model

Table 6 Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.905	27

The above Table 4.6 illustrates the validation of the model by assessing the reliability of the research constructs. Reliability is critical for determining the consistency and dependability of the measurements utilized in the study. Cronbach's Alpha is applied to evaluate internal consistency, with a threshold of 0.7 or above indicating robust construct reliability. As shown in the table, the calculated Cronbach's Alpha is

0.905, significantly exceeding the acceptable threshold. This high value signifies excellent internal consistency among the 27 items measured, underscoring the strong reliability and validity of the constructs employed in the research framework.

Hypotheses Testing

Correlations Analysis

Table 7 Correlations

		Consumer Online Purchase Intention
Green Consumer Attitude	Pearson Correlation	.758
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.004
	N	253
Ethical Brand Perception	Pearson Correlation	.822

	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002
	N	253
Digital Marketing Green Campaigns	Pearson Correlation	.598
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.003
	N	253
Trustworthiness	Pearson Correlation	.799
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001
	N	253
Social Influence	Pearson Correlation	.869
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	253
Consumer Online Purchase Intention	Pearson Correlation	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	
	N	253

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The above Table 4.7 demonstrates the relationship and correlation between the dependent variable (Consumer Online Purchase Intention) and the independent variables. It uses the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) to measure the strength and direction of the linear relationship. All correlations are statistically significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed), indicating meaningful associations between the variables.

Green Consumer Attitude and Consumer Online Purchase Intention: A strong positive correlation ($r = 0.758$, $sig = 0.004$) suggests that a favourable green consumer attitude significantly influences online purchase intentions.

Ethical Brand Perception and Consumer Online Purchase Intention: This variable exhibits a very strong positive correlation ($r = 0.822$, $sig = 0.002$), indicating that ethical brand perceptions are key drivers of purchase intentions.

Digital Marketing Green Campaigns and Consumer Online Purchase Intention: A moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.598$, $sig = 0.003$) shows that green campaigns contribute to purchase intentions but with less impact compared to other variables.

Trustworthiness and Consumer Online Purchase Intention: This factor has a strong positive correlation ($r = 0.799$, $sig = 0.001$), emphasizing the importance of trust in influencing online purchasing behaviour.

Social Influence and Consumer Online Purchase Intention: Social influence demonstrates the strongest correlation ($r = 0.869$, $sig = 0.000$), highlighting its critical role in shaping online purchase intentions.

These results underscore the significance of these variables in enhancing consumer online purchase intentions.

Regression Analysis
Table 8 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.788 ^a	.633	.613	.56158

a. Predictors: (Constant), Social Influence, Trustworthiness, Green_Consumer_Attitude, Ethical_Brand_Perception, Digital_Marketing_Green_Campaigns

Table 9 ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	70.026	5	23.342	107.528	.000 ^b
	Residual	51.882	247	.217		

	Total	121.907	252		
a. Dependent Variable: Consumer_Online_Purchase_Intention					
b. Predictors: (Constant), Social_Influence, Trustworthiness, Green_Consumer_Attitude, Ethical_Brand_Perception, Digital_Marketing_Green_Campaigns					

Table 10 Coefficientsa

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.241	.207		5.921	.000
	Green Consumer Attitude	.541	.063	.110	1.746	.001
	Ethical Brand Perception	.703	.060	.036	.568	.000
	Digital Marketing Green Campaigns	.430	.044	.043	.677	.004
	Trustworthiness	.614	.058	.114	1.788	.003
	Social Influence	.569	.072	.060	.953	.000
a. Dependent Variable: Consumer_Online_Purchase_Intention						

The above three tables (Table 4.8, Table 4.9, and Table 4.10) present the regression analysis conducted to assess the relationship between independent variables (Green Consumer Attitude, Ethical Brand Perception, Digital Marketing Green Campaigns, Trustworthiness, and Social Influence) and the dependent variable (Consumer Online Purchase Intention).

The model summary (Table 4.8) shows that the R value is 0.788, indicating a strong positive relationship between the predictors and Consumer Online Purchase Intention. The R² value of 0.633 reveals that 63.3% of the variation in Consumer Online Purchase Intention can be explained by the independent variables. The standard error of the estimate is 0.56158, suggesting a relatively low degree of error in the predictions.

The ANOVA results (Table 4.9) demonstrate the statistical significance of the model. The F-statistic is 107.528 (p = 0.000), indicating that the independent variables as a whole significantly predict Consumer Online Purchase Intention. This confirms the overall model's validity in explaining the variance in the dependent variable.

The coefficients table (Table 4.10) provides the unstandardized and standardized coefficients for each independent variable. Among the predictors, Green Consumer Attitude (B = 0.541, p = 0.001), Ethical Brand Perception (B = 0.703, p = 0.000), Digital Marketing Green Campaigns (B = 0.430, p = 0.004), and Trustworthiness (B = 0.614, p = 0.003) all show statistically significant positive relationships with Consumer Online Purchase Intention, suggesting that these variables positively influence purchase intentions. However, Social Influence (B = 0.569, p = 0.000) also demonstrates a significant positive effect, confirming that it is another key factor in shaping online purchase decisions.

In conclusion, the regression analysis reveals that Green Consumer Attitude, Ethical Brand Perception, Digital Marketing Green Campaigns, Trustworthiness, and Social Influence are all significant predictors of Consumer Online Purchase Intention. The model effectively explains a substantial portion of the variability in consumer behaviour, with Trustworthiness and Ethical Brand Perception being particularly influential.

Hypotheses Assessment Summary

Table 11 Hypotheses Assessment

Hypotheses	Critical Value (p-value)	Decision
H1: Green consumer attitude significantly impact the consumer purchase intention in the digital marketplace.	.001	Accepted

H2: Ethical brand perception significantly impact the consumer purchase intention in the digital marketplace.	.000	Accepted
H3: Digital Marketing Green Campaigns significantly impact the consumer purchase intention in the digital marketplace.	.004	Accepted
H4: E-commerce trustworthiness significantly impact the consumer purchase intention in the digital marketplace.	.003	Accepted
H5: Social influence significantly impact the consumer purchase intention in the digital marketplace.	.000	Accepted

The hypothesis testing results confirm that all five proposed hypotheses are supported by the data, with each showing statistically significant relationships between the independent variables and the dependent variable, consumer purchase intention in the digital marketplace.

According to H1, the degree to which a consumer's attitude is green has a considerable impact on the intention to purchase. The p-value of 0.001 clearly accepts it and indicates a close positive relationship between green consumer attitudes and online purchase decisions. Likewise, for H2, which shows how the effect of ethical brand perception influences attitude toward purchase intentions, a p-value of 0.000 confirms the statistical importance of the two.

H3 has examined the influence of digital marketing green campaigns and found a p-value of 0.004 which leads to the acceptance of this hypothesis. Thus, sustainable marketing efforts can greatly affect consumer behavior. In this case, H4 considerably links trustworthiness in e-commerce with purchase intention (0.003), further underlining the vital role that trust plays in online shopping environments.

H5, which tests for the effect of social influence on consumer purchase intention, gave a p-value of 0.000, and therefore the hypothesis was accepted. This shows that social influence indeed is a strong determinant of consumer decisions in the digital marketplace. All these contributions, therefore, give substantiating evidence of the significant role played by sustainability, ethics, trust, and social spheres in online consumer behavior.

Conclusion, Discussion, Implications, Limitations and Recommendations

Conclusion

The purpose of this research was to examine the impact of sustainable and ethical e-commerce marketing on consumers' buying behaviour in

the online environment. From this finding, it is evident that, and though consumers are becoming more environmentally and ethically concerned, their buying decisions are mainly guided on how a business organisation's marketing strategies correspond with these aspects. The study establishes that transparency, supply chain, and sustainability are critical aspects that define how firms in the e-commerce market should market their products. All these aspects relate the business to customer's concern while at the same time building brand image and credibility. The study also supports the features of legality, pointing out that data privacy regulation, concern for the environment, and labour relations affect the competition in e-commerce internationally. The paper adds to the body of writings on sustainable marketing and re-emphasizes the fact that consumers use extrinsic cues and intrinsic values when making decisions. As for now, let e-commerce is being one of the successes that have changed the way people think about the convenience and accessibility of purchasing; the rapidity of its development now asks about the further changes in practices that have to be focused on sustainability and ethical aspects. Finally, the research points to the reality of dynamic shifts and change that require new strategies in communicating with the targeted and sceptical public with high ethical standards for business practices in an environment that is becoming ever more heavily controlled by government regulations.

Discussion

The discussion further elaborates on the implications of this study's findings in the usefulness of considering sustainability and ethical issues while marketing e-commerce according to this discussion. These findings suggest that consumers favour those businesses that integrate and adjust their actions with

environmental and social sustainability. This preference can be explained in reference to social trends experienced globally that show consumption is increasingly centring on brands that can be held to account. The application of the Diffusion of Innovation Theory and the SVAB Model has given a theoretical direction to the study of consumer values, attitudes and behaviours. The implication of the research is that ethical and sustainable marketing strategies and messages serve the broader interest of enhancing brand image and being persuasive in consumers' choices. Furthermore, the research identifies how these strategies are problematic for business as they present trade-offs on how they can be adopted, for example, cost-performance trade-off. On one hand, consumers benefit from prompt delivery, and on the other hand, store owners contribute to waste and energy issues; however, new and efficient approaches to packaging, logistics, and the disclosure of supply chain networks reduce such concerns. Moreover, the discussion focuses on the technological aspects as sources of consumers' perceptions, stating that technology both acts as both enablers and barriers in the promotion of sustainable consumption. The following section also ties up the theoretical framework of the study with the practical implications of sustainable and ethical e-commerce marketing tactics.

Implications

Therefore, this research is monumental to e-commerce organizations, governments and customers. Thus, using sustainability and ethics into the marketing and operation strategies is significant for businesses according to the findings. Implementation of such practices can provide competitive benefits which embrace increase in brand image and reputation, customer loyalty and company distinction among the competitors. Furthermore, the study acknowledges the general aspect of the effective use of digital marketing platforms in creating awareness and changing people's decisions, and therefore, it encourages the use of the platforms in supporting sustainable purchasing decisions. In view of these findings, the development and implementation of e-commerce policies for regulating the sector remain paramount for policy makers. This encompasses post-consumer recycled products use on packaging, reduced

energy consumption in operations, and labor rights. It indicates that through promulgation of his rules and regulations, the law can encourage organizations to embrace sustainable systems while at the same time shield the consumer. Consumers are also a major participant that have a lot of influence since they will form a massive pressure group which would call for manufacturers to adopt green production. The study states that it will be useful to conduct the additional consumer education campaigns about the environmental and ethical consequences of purchasing the products online. Furthermore, it has implications for future research for the employment of e-commerce for ethical and sustainable business practices in the academic domain. Therefore, this study helps to progress the knowledge regarding the interrelatedness and the improvement of business and consumers' values for a more sustainable e-business environment.

Limitations

However, it is vitally important to understand that this study has certain limitations to it. This study has some limitations, of which the use of convenience sampling may have introduced some biases since the respondents were selected based on their availability and willingness to participate in the study and not through a systematic procedure. This may also restrict the applicability of the results to other members of the public. Also, the three-study depended on self-reported data through questionnaires might worsen socially desirable bias where participant gave desirable instead of real answers. The last is related to the issue of the scope of the research: this research selected the consumers' attitude and behaviour regarding electronic commerce in certain context and did not encompass the unlimited number of contexts of the global environment. More to the point, using a quantitative approach the study may not have fully captured the Subjectivity, comments, and motives that drive the consumers which could have been achieved best by a qualitative study. The dynamicity of e-commerce and regulations is another challenge, the findings of this research may be invalid since e commerce is a rapidly growing field with constantly developing technologies and regulations changing from year to year. However, the study provides sound

empirical background for the creation of an effectively more comprehensive study, calling for increased employment of mixed research methodology and more diverse sampling techniques to support the quantitative results provided herein.

Recommendations

Accordingly, the follow recommendations can be suggested for the businesses, policymakers, and researchers. That is why for the commercial entities, it is extremely important to pursue elaborate sustainability concepts, including regarding the use of disposable materials, the optimization of energy facilities for delivering goods and services, and respecting workers' rights. Such campaigns should be openly marketed using effective online media to ensure customer understanding and tour operator's loyalty. Taking relationships with environmental organizations to the next level and getting certifications can add to brand legitimacy. Government should encourage companies to follow the green policies by offering various incentives on the companies that are environmentally friendly while the companies that are not compliant with availing policies on the environment and labor should be penalized heavily. Each case revolves around certain features of electronic commerce that has to be managed or coordinated and it has been found that regulations should be updated periodically and changed according to the needs that arise with the newer issues of the time such as the data privacy concerns or the potential carbon footprints of e-commerce operations and more. Concerning the research agenda for future studies, researchers should find out how the practices of sustainable e-commerce affects consumer behaviour and firm's performance. The use of both qualitative and quantitative methods can give a deeper understanding of the psychological and emotional aspect of the consumers. Moreover, extending the study to more locations can provide with broader multicultural perception of the tendencies. Last but not the least, more extensive consumer-awareness information crusades should be initiated so as to enable the public to understand the environmental/ethical consequences of online consumerism so as to arrive at a rational

and sensible decision the next time they are in the cyber world to shopping.

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